

High-Fidelity Adjoint-based Aircraft Shape Optimization with Aeroelastic Trimming and Engine Coupling

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Summary

A high-fidelity adjoint-based aerodynamic shape optimization process has been set up that engages the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes solver TAU and couples with the finite element solver Nastran and the thermodynamic engine cycle analysis tool GTlab-Performance. A so-called CAD-ROM, which is a reduced order model representation of a parametric computer-aided design model, is used as shape parameterization. The process enables a gradient-based aeroelastic optimization of full aircraft configurations with powered engines. Therein, a trimming module ensures that each optimization iteration is feasible by imposing an equilibrium of forces and moments. The process is embedded within FlowSimulator, an environment dedicated to efficient multi-physics simulations on high-performance computing clusters. The shape sensitivities are consistently derived by coupling the discrete flow, mesh and structural adjoints and by accounting for a trim-correction of the objective functional. The optimization process has been demonstrated for a cruise range optimization of a generic transport aircraft model. The range can be increased by approximately five percent within the first six optimization iterations by adapting the wing shape defined by a 126-dimensional wing section Bspline parameterization.

Keywords: *adjoint, RANS, shape, optimization, aerodynamic, aeroelastic, engine, trimming.*

1 Introduction

As stated in the current European Aviation Environmental Report,¹ the aviation sector today already accounts for three percent of the world wide greenhouse gas emissions and long term forecasts indicate that the global air traffic is continuing to increase. In the face of the looming environmental crisis, the aviation sector as a whole has to reduce its ecological footprint. New technologies like natural laminar wings, more and all electric aircraft or ultra-high bypass ratio engines could help to achieve ambitious environmental targets. An efficient and economically reasonable integration of such singledisciplinary technology demonstrators in full aircraft configurations remains a difficult task. Multidisciplinary

Design Optimization (MDO) is seen as a key driver for a holistic aircraft design that could contribute to overcome some of the associated problems. By constructing numerical models for all relevant disciplines, a mathematical description of the design space can be set up. The design space is defined by all available degrees of freedom, but also by all necessary constraints. It can be explored and exploited without the need for time and cost intensive experimental models and prototypes. However, the prerequisites are sufficiently accurate models which require that high-fidelity numerical methods are employed.

Along these lines, several MDO environments are currently implemented within the DLR project VicToria. The process described in this paper focuses on gradient-based aerodynamic shape optimization under the

influence of steady-state aeroelastic effects and powered engine coupling. By relying on high-fidelity numerical tools suitable for large-scale computations and a coupled adjoint-based sensitivity analysis, the presented process can be considered as a state-of-the-art MDO component. The process is entirely integrated in the Cybermatrix² framework and the fully gradient-based MDO tool chain³ developed in VicToria. Furthermore, it has been partly used as a benchmark process to evaluate OpenMDAO's Modular Analysis and Unified Derivatives (MAUD) capabilities in the work of Backhaus et al.⁴

2 Methodology

The primal-adjoint consistent optimization process is drafted in Figure 1. The process is driven by a gradient-based optimization algorithm which maximizes the cruise range of an aircraft with respect to a set of shape design parameters. With every optimization iteration, the parameterization produces a shape displacement field on an auxiliary mesh and, if required, analytical geometrical sensitivities, see Section 2.1. Furthermore, each design candidate suggested by the optimization algorithm is trimmed by a Newton-based algorithm which adjusts the aerodynamic angle of attack, the deflection of the Horizontal Tail Plane (HTP) and the engine thrust requirement in order to impose a full equilibrium of forces and moments on the flying aircraft. All force and moments acting on the aircraft during the cruise mission are accounted for: aerodynamic loads, gravitational forces and thrust forces resulting from the aerodynamic high-fidelity simulation of the engine inlet and exhaust streams. The structural model has detailed information on the mass of the load carrying structure, systems, payload, fuel and the center of gravity. These are all used for the balance equations. The required trim Jacobian is updated by Broyden's bad method. The trim convergence is improved by using the Aitken method for accelerating vector sequences. This implicit trimming procedure has the advantage that each optimization iteration is feasible, i.e. the optimization process can be stopped at any point and the objective functional improvements gained so far can be considered usable and valuable, since all constraints necessary for a steady state cruise flight are met. Previous work of the authors⁵ has shown that for the presented optimization problem such an implicit trimming procedure finds the same optimal design regions as an explicit trimming approach in which the top level optimization algorithm controls in addition to the shape design parameters also the trim parameters and handles the trim constraints. For the sensitivity computation, the trimming loop is replaced by a trim-correction routine. This is necessary, as for the objective functional gradient information requested by the unconstrained optimization algorithm has to account for the infinitesimal trim-defect. This defect is induced with the shape parameter variation of the next optimization iteration.

After the trim algorithm suggests a new trim vector, which also contains the current cruise thrust request, the thermodynamic engine performance model is analyzed, see Section 2.2. The results of this analysis are the current Thrust Specific Fuel Consumption (TSFC) and the thermodynamic states. These are used to define the engine inflow and exhaust boundary conditions of the high-fidelity aerodynamic model. Required gradients of the engine model are obtained by central finite differences.

For each trim candidate, several aeroelastic coupling iterations are performed. At first, the aerodynamic model is analyzed. It receives the current angle of attack from the trim algorithm and the engine boundary conditions from the engine model. The shape parameterization displacements generated on the aforementioned auxiliary mesh are interpolated and added to the jig-shape baseline surface mesh of the aerodynamic model. These parameterization displacements are actually updated to account for the current HTP deflection predicted by the trim algorithm. Structural displacements, which were generated by the structural model analysis in the previous aeroelastic coupling iteration, are also interpolated and added to the baseline jig-shape surface mesh of the aerodynamic model. With this procedure, the interpolation matrices are computed just once for the baseline jig-shape meshes and remain constant throughout an optimization run. The two displacement interpolation matrices are constructed by means of a Moving Least Squares (MLS) interpolation method. This is a mesh-free approach which first constructs local polynomial fits and then assembles them continuously over the whole domain by generating a global MLS interpolation matrix. Data on given target points is forced to be interpolated and the method is by built conservative. The parameterization and structural displacement data stored on the aerodynamic baseline jig-shape mesh is used to first deform the surface mesh and then propagate the surface deformation into the volume mesh. After the mesh displacement is completed, the flow field is computed using restart solutions from previous coupling iterations to speed-up the solution process. Integral aerodynamic coefficients as well as aerodynamic loads can be extracted from the updated flow solution. The mesh deformation and flow computation for the aerodynamic model are described in detail in Section 2.3.

In the next aeroelastic coupling step, the aerodynamic loads are interpolated from the aerodynamic model surface mesh onto the structural model mesh. Since the transpose of the structural displacements interpolation matrix is used for the loads interpolation, the aeroelastic coupling procedure can be stated to be conservative and consistent. The structural analysis is performed as described in Section 2.4. With the resulting structural displacements, the next aeroelastic coupling step can be computed.

The computation of the total objective functional sensitivity w.r.t. to the shape parameters is performed in adjoint mode. Therefore, the flow, mesh and structural

adjoints of the mesh deformation tool and the flow and structural solvers are consistently coupled by virtue of a block-Gauss-Seidel method. The coupled adjoint method has been investigated already by several research teams,⁶⁻⁹ but is still in the focus of current research activities and of high interest to the aircraft industry. Therefore, a full sensitivity derivation is outlined in Section 2.5.

The backbone of the primal-adjoint process is the FlowSimulator environment for massively parallel multi-physics simulations on high-performance computing (HPC) clusters. It enables the handling of large data sets in a fully domain-parallel workflow by coupling disciplinary tools as so-called plugins to a central data manager. The data manager holds the data in-memory and helps to reduce time-consuming file I/O to a minimum. More FlowSimulator details and applications are described in the work of Reimer.¹⁰

Figure 1: Scheme of the primal-adjoint consistent optimization process.

2.1 Shape Parameterization

The parameterization strategy used in this paper relies on the so-called CAD-ROM approach, which has been originally introduced by Bobrowski et al.¹¹ and later was further investigated by the authors.¹² Following this approach, the geometry can be defined and parameterized using a CAD system which has great advantages such as robust surface intersection handling, no compromises between global and local shape control and implicit geometric constraint definitions when compared to the usual parameterization techniques. The CAD model is then replaced by a Reduced Order Model (ROM) representation of the parametric surfaces to streamline the optimization process. The CAD-ROM generation (offline mode) and evaluation (online mode) is conducted by DLR's Surrogate Modeling for AeRoData Toolbox SMARTy.

The offline phase requires a Design of Experiments (DoE) setup, which samples the design space defined by the CAD parameterization. For each DoE parameter sample, the CAD surfaces are updated and discretized using an auxiliary mesh having the same topology for each sample. Consequently, displacement fields relative to the baseline geometry can be extracted and assembled to a so-called snapshot matrix. By applying singular value decomposition to the snapshot matrix, a POD (Proper Orthogonal Decomposition) is obtained. The displacement fields of the auxiliary mesh can now be reconstructed by a weighted sum of POD modes, where the POD coefficients act as weights. Usually, the POD subspace is truncated to avoid numerical noise. During the online phase, the CAD-ROM has to predict surface displacements for arbitrary parameters. Therefore, the POD coefficients need to be interpolated using the DoE samples as training data. Once the interpolation coefficients have been determined, POD coefficients and thus displacement fields can be computed for each parameter combination. Radial basis functions with thin plate spline kernel are used as interpolation method.

The CAD-ROM is analytically differentiated and used consistently for the computation of geometric sensitivities.

2.2 Engine Model

The engine model used for the present study is a three-spool turbofan engine, which was designed once for an initial set of thrust requirements at the investigated flight conditions. The engine design is conducted with the DLR in-house program system GTlab (Gas Turbine laboratory), a framework for the design and analysis of aircraft engines and stationary gas turbines at various levels of detail. In the design process, all relevant engine operating points are taken into consideration. The turbo component behavior at off-design conditions is modeled by means of generic component maps which are scaled to match the design conditions of the engine cycle. For the efficiencies of the turbo components, the cooling air requirements of the turbines, the mechanical losses of shafts and the pressure

losses in ducts state-of-the-art technologies are assumed. The model-internal pressure losses occurring in the engine inlet, the bypass duct and nozzles are brought into agreement with an initial aerodynamic analysis performed with the high-fidelity flow solver TAU to ensure a correct pressure loss bookkeeping between the aerodynamic model and the engine performance model. Furthermore, it is ensured that the engine complies with all geometrical restrictions imposed by the given nacelle geometry.

After the initial engine design, the engine model is fixed and the engine performance can be evaluated for slightly changing cruise thrust requirements resulting from the optimization process. The module GTlab-Performance enables a fast simulation of thermodynamic cycles for steady state as well as transient operating conditions.¹³ For this paper, GTlab-Performance has been integrated into the optimization process, in order to represent the engine behavior in a detailed way. It provides inflow and exhaust boundary conditions for the aerodynamic model and operating point specific information on the fuel flow.

2.3 Aerodynamic Model

The compressible steady-state flow field is computed on unstructured median-dual grids by the finite-volume Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) code TAU¹⁴ developed at DLR. For this process, fully turbulent conditions are assumed and the negative extension of the Spalart-Allmaras (SA-neg) turbulence model is used. The second-order accurate discretization is based on a matrix-dissipative central convection scheme and Green-Gauss gradients for the viscous flux. The discretized set of equations governing the transport of mass, momentum, energy and the SA-neg transport variable are solved by an agglomeration multigrid method based on the full approximation scheme (FAS). Several implicit-Euler relaxation steps are applied on every grid level. The corresponding linear problems are treated by a symmetric forward-backward Gauss-Seidel (LUSGS) iteration. For employing the discrete adjoint method in TAU, the integral force and moment coefficients and the residual of the second-order accurate flow discretization are fully linearized w.r.t. the conservative flow variables including the Sa-neg turbulence model, but also w.r.t. to the mesh point coordinates. For the solution of the flow adjoint system, the adjoint-residual terms corresponding to the remote-stencil terms of the second-order discretization are reconstructed in two passes. Therefore, the memory requirements of the discrete adjoint method are similar to those of the non-linear flow solver. The discrete flow adjoint RANS problem is solved with a GMRES method, preconditioned by the linear counterpart to the FAS multigrid method. Multigrid smoothing, in turn, is performed by the implicit-Euler method, wherein the transposed of the primal LUSGS operator is applied. More details regarding the discrete flow adjoint implementation are provided in the work of Stück.¹⁵

Powered engines are modeled in the RANS simulation by applying flux-based boundary conditions in virtue of the approximate Riemann method of Roe, which is described by Stück and Heinrich.¹⁶ The engine boundary conditions are fully linearized to support the discrete adjoint sensitivity computations with TAU. Figure 2 gives a detailed image of the engine geometry the aerodynamic model. At the engine inlet, static pressure is prescribed and the remaining flow state is extrapolated according to the state equation for perfect gas. At the engine exhausts, isentropic conditions are assumed, the total pressures and temperatures are prescribed and the velocity is extrapolated from the inner domain. The static and total states that need to be prescribed are computed by a thermodynamic engine performance model according to the current thrust requirement. When such a strong coupling between aerodynamic and engine model is performed, the engine boundary condition planes are often denoted as Aerodynamic Interface Planes (AIP).

Figure 2: Turbofan engine used for the aerodynamic model.

The prescribed surface deformations coming from parameterization, HTP trimming and aeroelastic coupling are propagated into the volume mesh by means of a mesh deformation tool based on the theory of linear Elasticity Analogy (EA). The mesh is modeled as an elastic solid with a variable Young's modulus which is reciprocal to the volume of each mesh element in the baseline mesh. Small elements are artificially stiffened, whereas large elements absorb the deformation. The resulting linear elasticity equations are discretized by a Finite Element Method (FEM) and solved on the baseline mesh for each optimization, trim or aeroelastic iteration. The linear EA problem is self-adjoint and the stiffness matrix is symmetric meaning that the tool can be used without significant changes to set up and solve the mesh adjoint problem.

2.4 Structural Model

The tool-like aeroelastic structural design process cpacs-MONA was used for the initial structural FEM model generation within the presented process chain. The resulting model is called GFEM/dynamic and is shown in Figure 3. GFEM stands for global finite element model and dynamic implies the capability of the model to be used for dynamic analysis. The GFEM/dynamic is used with MSC Nastran SOL101 for both the aeroelastic coupling within the aerodynamic performance analysis

and the aeroelastic adjoint coupling for the sensitivity computation. The stiffness matrix for the linear static analysis is found to be symmetric. Since the linear FEM problem is self-adjoint, MSC Nastran SOL101 can be used with the same structural model equally in primal and adjoint mode by just exchanging the applied aerodynamic loads. Any additional loads, e.g. payload, fuel, systems, need to be deactivated in the adjoint mode, in case they are included in the structural model.

For this paper, cpacs-MONA generates six different mass cases comprising typical design masses and one cruise condition. For the mass cases the operating empty weight is combined with defined payload/passenger variations and fuel conditions leading to different positions of the center of gravity. For each mass case various load types are calculated. These include pull-up, push-down, yawing, rolling and quasi-stationary gust encounters for different flight levels and design speeds according to CS25.335. In total 1062 load cases are considered within the loads analysis part of cpacs-MONA for this process. For the loads analyses, MSC Nastran SOL144 is used. In order to select the design loads for the structural optimization, the so-called cutting loads for the shear force, the bending, and the torsional moments are estimated and analyzed for selected monitor stations. For the structural optimization MSC Nastran SOL200 is used. As design variables the thickness of the skin, spar webs and ribs is taken. The objective functional is to minimize the mass of the load carrying structure of the wing-like components. Various stress values as well as the aileron efficiency are considered as constraints. For detailed information about cpacs-MONA and its individual process steps, see Klimmek et al.¹⁷

Figure 3: GFEM/dynamic structural model generated by cpacs-MONA.

The described model generation, loads analysis and structural optimization were carried out once for the baseline geometry. The update of the GFEM/dynamic during the aerodynamic shape optimization process is skipped. This was done on the one hand to reduce the process complexity and run time, on the other hand because the shape changes targeted in this paper are assumed to be negligible as far as the structural model is concerned. It is presumed that the carrying structure still fits well into the outer wing shape and that the obtained shape changes have no to little effect on the lower-fidelity aerodynamic doublet lattice method model used in the cpacs-MONA

loads analysis.

In case of wing planform changes during the aerodynamic optimization, an update of the GFEM/dynamic becomes necessary and can be activated. This is shown by Abu-Zurayk et al.³ who employ the core module of this process (without engine coupling) within a gradient-based MDO framework.

2.5 Cost Functionals and Sensitivity Computation

The Breguet-Range R is defined by the cruise point velocity v_∞ , the gravitational constant g , the thrust-specific fuel consumption $TSFC$, the aerodynamic efficiency L/D , the cruise point fuel weight m_{fuel} and the cruise point initial total weight m_{tot} :

$$R = v_\infty \frac{1}{g} \frac{1}{TSFC} L/D \ln \left(\frac{m_{tot}}{m_{tot} - m_{fuel}} \right) \quad (1)$$

In the following steps, the range equation (1) is fully differentiated w.r.t. the shape parameters \mathbf{S} :

$$\frac{dR}{d\mathbf{S}} = k \left(\frac{d \frac{1}{TSFC}}{d\mathbf{S}} L/D + \frac{1}{TSFC} \frac{dL/D}{d\mathbf{S}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Constant terms are gathered by k :

$$k = v_\infty \frac{1}{g} \ln \left(\frac{m_{tot}}{m_{tot} - m_{fuel}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The weights are assumed constant, since only a cruise point is examined and no structural sizing is performed.

TSFC is computed by the engine model depending only on the cruise point thrust requirement τ . The engine thrust τ , the aerodynamic angle of attack α of the aircraft and the HTP deflection angle δ are the three trim parameters defining the trim vector \mathbf{T} :

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \delta \\ \tau \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

\mathbf{T} is adapted by the trim algorithm for each design candidate in order to satisfy the equilibrium of forces and moments around the aircraft. For the cruise mission, only three trim constraints, expressed by force or moment coefficients in a body-fixed frame x, y, z , have to be accounted for:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{fx} \\ C_{fz} \\ C_{my} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{fx, aero} + C_{fx, grav} \\ C_{fz, aero} + C_{fz, grav} \\ C_{my, aero} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (5)$$

The force and moment coefficients contain both contributions from aerodynamics and gravity. The aerodynamic forces and moments can be further decomposed into forces and moments integrated over the walls of the aircraft model, coming from pressure

differences and friction, and those integrated over the AIPs, resulting from pressure differences and momentum:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{fx, aero} \\ C_{fz, aero} \\ C_{my, aero} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{fx, wall} + C_{fx, AIP} \\ C_{fz, wall} + C_{fz, AIP} \\ C_{my, wall} + C_{my, AIP} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The gravity forces are based on the cruise point total weight, scaled by the dynamic pressure q and the reference area A_{ref} and are transformed from the geodesic into the aircraft's body-fixed frame:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{fx, grav} \\ C_{fy, grav} \\ C_{fz, grav} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\alpha) \frac{m_{tot} g}{q A_{ref}} \\ 0 \\ -\cos(\alpha) \frac{m_{tot} g}{q A_{ref}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Back to (2), the derivative of $TSFC$ w.r.t. \mathbf{S} is obtained by using the gradient trim correction procedure presented in detail by Merle et al.⁵ It gives among others the derivative of trim w.r.t. shape parameters:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{dL/D}{d\mathbf{S}} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{T}}{d\mathbf{S}} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} -1 & \frac{\partial L/D}{\partial \mathbf{T}} \\ \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial C_{fx}}{\partial \mathbf{T}} \\ & \frac{\partial C_{fz}}{\partial \mathbf{T}} \\ & \frac{\partial C_{my}}{\partial \mathbf{T}} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial L/D}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \\ \frac{\partial C_{fx}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \\ \frac{\partial C_{fz}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \\ \frac{\partial C_{my}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Note that the inverted matrix in (8) is only of dimension 4×4 , meaning that the computational effort for solving the system is very low. However, computing the partial derivatives assembling the system is a more difficult task, since steady-state aeroelastic effects have to be considered.

To be independent of the design space dimension given by the size of \mathbf{S} , a coupled aerostructural adjoint approach is used for this task. Therein, the cost functionals, which are the aerodynamic coefficients, are replaced by a Langrange function L . Its derivative w.r.t. \mathbf{S} gives:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{S}} = \lambda_M^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_{surf, para}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \quad (9)$$

The geometric sensitivity $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_{surf, para}}{\partial \mathbf{S}}$ on the parameterized aerodynamic surface mesh $\mathbf{x}_{surf, para}$ is computed analytically by the CAD-ROM. The mesh adjoint variable λ_M is obtained iteratively by solving the coupled aerostructural adjoint system using the block Gauß-Seidel

method:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{for } (k = 0; k < N; k++) \\ & \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A}{\partial \mathbf{w}} \right)^T \lambda_A^k = \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial \mathbf{w}} \right)^T - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{w}} \right)^T \mathbf{Q}^T \lambda_S^{k-1} \\ & \mathbf{Y}^k = \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right)^T - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right)^T \lambda_A^k \\ & \mathbf{K}_M^T \lambda_M^k = \mathbf{Y}^k - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right)^T \mathbf{Q}^T \lambda_S^{k-1} \\ & \mathbf{K}_S^T \lambda_S^k = -\mathbf{Q} \lambda_M^k \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The first row in (10) solves the aerodynamic adjoint problem in TAU, with the flow residual \mathbf{R}_A , the conservative variables \mathbf{w} and the aerodynamic loads \mathbf{f} . A lagged coupling is introduced by the structural adjoint variable λ_S which first needs to be interpolated from the structural outer mesh onto the aerodynamic surface mesh using the interpolation matrix \mathbf{Q}^T . The interpolation matrix is computed once by the MLS algorithm and held constant during the optimization, because the coupling relies on the baseline aerodynamic and structural jig shape meshes. This is consistent with the primal coupling procedure. \mathbf{Q} is used for the reverse interpolation, i.e. from structures to aerodynamics. I can be any of the three aerodynamic coefficients $C_{fx, aero}$, $C_{fz, aero}$, $C_{my, aero}$, meaning that (9) and (10) have to be solved three times. Note that the gravity contribution to the force and moment coefficients does not depend on \mathbf{S} , i.e. its derivative w.r.t. \mathbf{S} is zero. The aerodynamic adjoint subproblem in (10) is the most difficult to solve compared to the structural and mesh adjoint subproblems. Two main reasons are the high degree of freedom that scales with the aerodynamic volume mesh size and the stiff nature of the flow Jacobian $\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A}{\partial \mathbf{w}}$. Restarts for λ_A are used to speed up the solution runtime and to increase the solution robustness. The variable \mathbf{Y} holds the so-called metric sensitivity w.r.t. the aerodynamic mesh node coordinates \mathbf{x} and is computed by TAU. The third row in (10) solves the mesh adjoint problem set-up by the EA mesh deformation algorithm. The matrix \mathbf{K}_M represents the linear elasticity stiffness matrix. The last row in (10) solves the structural adjoint problem with the symmetric structural stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_S using MSC Nastran SOL101. Nastran receives the mesh adjoint variable λ_M as a load case. The block Gauss-Seidel algorithm converges usually after $k = 3$ to $k = 4$ iterations in the sense that the shape gradients resulting from (9) show only little variations with additional coupling iterations.

So far, the partial derivatives of the three aerodynamic coefficients w.r.t. \mathbf{S} have been discussed. The aerodynamic efficiency L/D is treated separately. It is computed from the pressure, friction and momentum integration over the aircraft walls and AIPs, but it also requires a streamtube correction term L/D_{tube} . This term basically ensures a proper thrust-drag-bookkeeping by accounting for forces acting on the powered engines inlet and exhaust streamtubes:

$$L/D = L/D_{aero} + L/D_{tube} \quad (11)$$

The first part of (11) can be computed from $C_{fx, aero}$ and $C_{fz, aero}$:

$$L/D_{aero} = \frac{-\sin(\alpha) C_{fx, aero} + \cos(\alpha) C_{fz, aero}}{\cos(\alpha) C_{fx, aero} + \sin(\alpha) C_{fz, aero}} \quad (12)$$

The second part of (11) depends on the inlet and exhausts mass flows and areas and on the engine orientation, i.e. the nose-up and toe-in installation angles. Since the engine is neither scaled nor rotated in this study, the derivative of L/D_{tube} w.r.t. \mathbf{S} is zero and the derivative of L/D gives:

$$\frac{\partial L/D}{\partial \mathbf{S}} = \frac{\sin(\alpha)^2 + \cos(\alpha)^2}{(\cos(\alpha) C_{fx, aero} + \sin(\alpha) C_{fz, aero})^2} \cdot \left(C_{fx, aero} \frac{\partial C_{fz, aero}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} - C_{fz, aero} \frac{\partial C_{fx, aero}}{\partial \mathbf{S}} \right) \quad (13)$$

By assembling the derivative of the aerodynamic efficiency from the aerodynamic coefficients gradients, the overall sensitivity computation for a design iteration is 25% faster as if four cost functionals were applied in the coupled aerostructural adjoint process.

For obtaining the partial derivatives of aerodynamic coefficients w.r.t. \mathbf{T} in (8) there are two options: either the trim Jacobian from the Broyden update method can be used or adjoint-based derivatives resulting from the coupled aerostructural adjoint process described before can be employed. The latter is done for derivatives w.r.t. δ , since the HTP deflection angle is very similar to a shape parameter and the geometric sensitivity is obtained from the CAD-ROM, just like for the shape parameters \mathbf{S} . As far as derivatives w.r.t. α are concerned, the aerodynamic part is as well obtained by the coupled aerostructural adjoint process, the gravity part is added as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C_{fx}}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial C_{fz}}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial C_{my}}{\partial \alpha} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C_{fx, aero}}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial C_{fz, aero}}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial C_{my, aero}}{\partial \alpha} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha) \frac{m_{rot} g}{q A_{ref}} \\ \sin(\alpha) \frac{m_{rot} g}{q A_{ref}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Derivatives w.r.t. τ are taken from the Broyden update which gives a good estimate, since the aerodynamic coefficients are approximately linear dependent.

The last unknown partial derivative in (8) is that of the aerodynamic performance L/D w.r.t. \mathbf{T} . Again, the derivative w.r.t. δ comes from the coupled aerostructural adjoint process, similar to (13). The derivative w.r.t. α is given by

$$\frac{\partial L/D}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{\sin(\alpha)^2 + \cos(\alpha)^2}{(\cos(\alpha) C_{fx, aero} + \sin(\alpha) C_{fz, aero})^2} \cdot \left(C_{fx, aero} \left(\frac{\partial C_{fz, aero}}{\partial \alpha} - C_{fz, aero} \right) - C_{fz, aero} \left(\frac{\partial C_{fx, aero}}{\partial \alpha} + C_{fx, aero} \right) \right) \quad (15)$$

For the derivative w.r.t. τ , the Broyden update of the aerodynamic coefficients is used. As before, the derivative of the streamtube correction is omitted:

$$\frac{\partial L/D}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\sin(\alpha)^2 + \cos(\alpha)^2}{(\cos(\alpha) C_{fx, aero} + \sin(\alpha) C_{fz, aero})^2} \cdot \left(C_{fx, aero} \frac{\partial C_{fz, aero}}{\partial \tau} - C_{fz, aero} \frac{\partial C_{fx, aero}}{\partial \tau} \right) \quad (16)$$

After computing all partial derivatives in (8) and solving the system, the chain rule is used to obtain the first derivative in (2):

$$\frac{d \frac{1}{TSFC}}{d \mathbf{S}} = \frac{d \frac{1}{TSFC}}{d \mathbf{T}} \frac{d \mathbf{T}}{d \mathbf{S}} \quad (17)$$

The term $\frac{d \frac{1}{TSFC}}{d \mathbf{T}}$ is non-zero only for derivatives w.r.t. τ and is obtained by applying central finite differences with GTlab-Performance.

The second derivative $\frac{dL/D}{d \mathbf{S}}$ in (2) is also resulting from (8), meaning that the differentiation of the Breguet-Range is complete.

Having all the gradient contributions at hand to assemble the range derivative (2), the formulation of the optimization objective can be switched to maximize the aerodynamic efficiency L/D or to minimize the fuel consumption m_{fuel} , depending on the optimization scenario.

3 Problem Setup

The process described above is applied in this paper to a generic multidisciplinary research test case representing a typical configuration for a modern long range wide-body aircraft, see Figure 4.

Since on the aerodynamics side only the cruise condition is analyzed, the computational domain is defined by a half-model consisting of an unstructured mesh with 10.8 Mio mesh nodes generated for the baseline geometry with the Centaur Software. On the structural side, a full model with approximately 20,000 plate elements is used.

The cruise range is maximized for a single-point cruise mission at Mach 0.83 and a flight altitude of 38,000 ft by optimizing 126 Bspline control point positions on seven span-wise distributed wing sections. There are nine control points per upper and lower wing section and their degree of freedom is restricted to the vertical aircraft axis. The

Figure 4: Generic transport aircraft model used as process demonstrator in jig-shape (transparent) and cruise flight-shape (solid).

wing leading and trailing edges are fixed, i.e. a variation of the twist distribution is prohibited. As described above, the original B-spline parameterization is defined by a CAD system, which is replaced in the optimization process by a CAD-ROM representation.

The L^2 norm of TAU's density residual is converged by six orders of magnitude. A fixed number of three aeroelastic coupling iterations is performed per trim iteration and a constant relaxation factor of 0.7 is applied to each structural displacements update. The trim tolerances for the full equilibrium state are set to 0.1 force or moment counts with a count being equal to a coefficient value of 0.0001. The aeroelastic wing tip deflection converges to the end of the trimming loop to a value smaller than 1 mm. With this approach, the aerodynamic coefficients can be evaluated in total with an accuracy of approximately ± 0.1 force counts. The TAU flow adjoint solution is also converged by six orders of magnitude. For each of the three aerodynamic cost functionals, a fixed number of three aeroelastic adjoint coupling iterations is performed. A Conjugate Gradient (CG) method is driving the optimization process.

4 Optimization

The optimization was conducted using 244 cores of the DLR case cluster which is equipped with Intel Xeon X5670 processors with a base frequency of 2.93 GHz. Within six days, 22 optimization iterations were performed, whereof nine iteration evaluations were enhanced by a gradient computation. The optimization reaches after the first six optimization iterations 99.6% of the final range improvement of 4.91%, see Figure 5. This means that the final improvement level was reached in less than 40h wall clock time. Note that one optimization iteration is here referred to as a function call from the CG algorithm.

The shape changes introduced by the optimization algorithm act basically on the inner wing, as seen in Figure 6. In this region, the wing section thicknesses decrease slightly and the camber increases which leads in total to an increased rear-loading. The displacement magnitudes are in a range of -56 mm to 32 mm and do not hit any imposed design space boundaries.

A major effect of the shape changes concerns the

Figure 5: Optimization history.

Figure 6: Normal component of optimal shape displacements seen from bottom (left) and top (right) view. Blue indicates that the surface is pushed-in, red indicates that the surface is pulled-out.

generated wave drag. Figure 7 shows the pressure distribution on the baseline and the optimized aircraft surfaces. The strength of the supersonic shock wave is significantly reduced, most of all in the mid-wing region.

5 Conclusions

An aerodynamic shape optimization process is presented that uses the RANS solver TAU, the FEM solver Nastran and the thermodynamic engine cycle analysis tool GTlab-Performance. For the aerodynamic model, powered engines are simulated and coupled to the engine model and a force-consistent and -conservative coupling with the structural model is performed. A trimming algorithm ensures that each optimization iteration is feasible by controlling the aerodynamic angle of attack, the HTP deflection angle and the engine thrust. The backbone of the process is the HPC-oriented multi-physics environment FlowSimulator.

In order to demonstrate the presented capabilities, the cruise range of a generic transport aircraft model is increased by approximately 5% by a gradient-based CG

Figure 7: Pressure coefficient comparison between baseline (left) and optimized (right) configuration.

algorithm using sensitivities provided by an efficient and consistent coupled adjoint-based sensitivity computation. The parameterization employed for this study is a ROM representation of 126 CAD-based B-spline wing section parameters. By using the adjoint approach, the process is completely independent of the number of design parameters so that the parameterization can be easily extended to support changes in wing planform, belly fairing, pylon, engine positioning, engine size, nacelle contour etc. However, many of the mentioned changes imply an update of the structural model including the loads and sizing process, which is performed just once for the baseline using the tool cpacs-MONA. Also the engine design, initially performed with the software package GTlab, needs to be scaled. Large shape variations and automated updates of the structural and the engine models are currently tackled in two MDO environments developed within DLR's ongoing project VicToria, where the process presented in this paper is integrated as a core module.

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References

- [1] EASA, EEA, E. European aviation environmental report. Technical report, European Union Commission for Transport, (2019).
- [2] Ilic, C., Merle, A., Abu-Zurayk, M., Leitner, M., Schulze, M., Schuster, A., Petsch, M., and Gottfried, S. Cybermatrix: A link between classical aircraft design and formal multidisciplinary optimization approaches. (EUROGEN Conference, Guimarães, Portugal, 2019).
- [3] Abu-Zurayk, M., Merle, A., Ilic, C., Schulze, M., and Klimmek, T. Aerostructural optimization of trimmed transport aircraft; comparison of different optimization formulations. (EUROGEN Conference, Guimarães, Portugal, 2019).
- [4] Backhaus, T., Gottfried, S., Ilic, C., Merle, A., and Stück, A. Integration of high-fidelity analysis tools in mdo frameworks for hpc. (AIAA/ISSMO Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization Conference, Fort Worth, TX, USA, 2019).
- [5] Merle, A., Stück, A., and Rempke, A. An adjoint-based aerodynamic shape optimization strategy for trimmed aircraft with active engines. (AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference, Denver, CO, USA, 2017).
- [6] Sanchez, R., Albring, T., Palacios, R., Gauger, N., Economon, T., and Alonso, J. Coupled adjoint-based sensitivities in large-displacement fluid-structure interaction using algorithmic differentiation. *Int J Numer Meth Engng* **113**(7), 1081–1107 (2018).
- [7] Blondeau, C., Achard, T., Girodroux-Lavigne, P., and Ohayon, R. Recent achievements towards aero-structure gradient computation using high-fidelity cfd-csm in the onera elsa software. (IFASD Conference, Saint Peterburg, Russia, 2015).
- [8] Zhang, Z. and Zingg, D. Efficient monolithic solution algorithm for high-fidelity aerostructural analysis and optimization. *AIAA Journal* **56**(3), 1251–1265 (2017).
- [9] Kenway, G., Kennedy, G., and Martins, J. Scalable parallel approach for high-fidelity steady-state aeroelastic analysis and adjoint derivative computations. *AIAA Journal* **52**(5), 935–951 (2014).
- [10] Reimer, L. The flowsimulator - a software framework for cfd-related multidisciplinary simulations. (European NAFEMS Conference, Munich, Germany, 2015).
- [11] Bobrowski, K., Ferrer, E., Valero, E., and Barnewitz, H. Aerodynamic shape optimization using geometry surrogates and adjoint method. *AIAA Journal* **55**(10), 3304–3317 (2017).
- [12] Merle, A., Ronzheimer, A., Bekemeyer, P., Görtz, S., Keye, S., and Reimer, L. Gradient-based optimization of a flexible long-range transport aircraft using a

- high-dimensional cad-rom parameterization. (DLRK Conference, Friedrichshafen, Germany, 2018).
- [13] Becker, R.-G., Wolters, F., Nauroz, M., and Otten, T. Development of a gas turbine performance code and its application to preliminary design. (DLRK Conference, Bremen, Germany, 2011).
- [14] Kroll, N., Langer, S., and Schwöppe, A. The dlr flow solver tau - status and recent algorithmic developments. (AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting, National Harbor, MD, USA, 2014).
- [15] Stück, A. Dual-consistency study for green-gauss gradient schemes in an unstructured navier-stokes method. *J Comput Phys* **350**(10), 530–549 (2017).
- [16] Stück, A. and Heinrich, R. Flugsimulation des getrimmten flugzeugs bei aktivem triebwerk. (STAB DGLR Conference, Munich, Germany, 2014).
- [17] Klimmek, T., Schulze, M., Abu-Zurayk, M., Ilic, C., and Merle, A. cpacs-mona – an independent and in high-fidelity based mdo tasks integrated process for the structural and aeroelastic design of aircraft configurations. (IFASD Conference, Savannah, GA, USA, 2019).